

ENTREPRENEURSHIP SKILLS AND CAREER SUCCESS AMONG GRADUATE FASHION DESIGN PRACTITIONERS IN OYO STATE

Lilian FAMOROTI¹ & Prof. Senimetu ILEUMA²

^{1,2}Department of Art and Social Science Education, Faculty of Education
Lead City University Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria
ileumassenimetu@icu.edu.ng

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Abstract

This study examined entrepreneurship skills and career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State. Literature shows that many graduate fashion designers are not achieving success and satisfaction in their career. There is also scarcity of studies on the influence of entrepreneurship skills on career success. The descriptive survey research design was employed. The population comprised all graduate fashion design practitioners (1,445) in Lagelu, Kajola and Ibadan North LGAs out of which 821 were sampled using Yamane sampling technique. Questionnaire titled – “Entrepreneurship Skills and Career Success Questionnaire (ESCSQ) ($\alpha = .814$)” was used to collect data. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Results showed moderate level of career success in areas of acquisition of assets ($\bar{x} = 2.530$), family needs attainment ($\bar{x} = 2.530$), and career satisfaction ($\bar{x} = 2.533$) and low level in area of employment generation ($\bar{x} = 2.409$). Results showed moderate level of technical skills ($\bar{x} = 2.801$), business management skills ($\bar{x} = 2.878$) and personal skills ($\bar{x} = 2.733$). Hypotheses revealed significant joint contribution of entrepreneurship skills (technical, business management and personal skills) on career success ($F_{6, 814} = 8.853, P < 0.05; R = .263; R^2 = .069; \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .065$). Furthermore, technical skills ($\beta = .176; t = 4.892; P < 0.05$), business management skills ($\beta = .165; t = 3.429; P < 0.05$), and personal skills ($\beta = .144; t = 2.925; P < 0.05$) all had significant relative influence on career success. It was concluded that moderate level of technical, business management and personal skills of the graduate fashion design practitioners are responsible for their moderate level of career success in areas of acquisition of assets, family needs attainment, and career satisfaction and low level in area of employment generation. It was recommended amongst others that the graduate fashion design practitioners should attend workshops and trainings to boost their entrepreneurship for career success.

Keywords: Fashion Design Practice Entrepreneurship skills, Career success

Introduction

Fashion design practice is a career associated with designing and making of cloths and dresses to cover the human body for protection and beautification (Nzei, 2022). Fashion design practice is one major entrepreneurial venture that both male and female graduates in Nigeria including Oyo state have delved into for several reasons such as interests, passion, and most especially the inability to get jobs (unemployment) in public and private sectors after graduation (Aduwa, 2020). As a result of these reasons, several graduates have decided to build a career in various

entrepreneurial ventures such as fashion design practice with the sole aim of achieving career success.

Career success which could be objective (extrinsic) or subjective (intrinsic) is the favourable material and psychological results that a graduate fashion design practitioner have achieved from fashion design practice (Das & Chandrasekaran, 2024). Objective perspective on career success takes the tangible facets of graduate fashion design practitioner's career into account, such as ability to acquire assets (lands, houses, machines, and etcetera), generate employment for others, and meet family needs with ease (Nexhip et al., 2023). However, intrinsic or subjective career success is a graduate fashion design practitioner's internal satisfaction with his or her work or career (Farla et al., 2021).

Many graduate fashion design practitioners ventured into fashion design career with the hope of attaining career success. However, this has not been the case as some graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo state are yet to attain intrinsic and/or extrinsic career success. Literature is replete with evidence of low career success among some graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo state (Adegbenle, 2021; Adeleke & Ojewale, 2023; Ashamu & Olateju, 2023; Ayodele, 2021; Obialo & Adelere, 2023; Oghenovo, 2022; Osuntayo, 2017). Several reasons for the cause of low career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo state have been proffered. Most of them include - entrepreneurial training, empowerment, environmental factors, and apprenticeship training (Adeleke & Ojewale, 2023; Ashamu & Olateju, 2023; Ayodele, 2021; Osuntayo, 2017). However, crucial factor such as the influence of entrepreneurship skills on career success of graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo state has not been given adequate attention in literature.

In the context of this study, entrepreneurial skills are competencies related to creativity, innovation, personal characteristics, practical, problem solving, communication, and marketing that enable graduate fashion design practitioners to design, and construct clothes, communicate and relate well with clients, and market finished products in fashion design enterprise in Oyo state (Nzei, 2022; Paul-Mgbeafulike, 2021). These skills are required by graduate fashion design entrepreneurs for profitability in the fashion design enterprise in Oyo state. They include - technical, business management, and personal skills.

Technical skills focuses on graduate fashion design practitioner's capacity to use technological processes, systems, equipment and materials and transfer knowledge and skills to new situations (Eteng et al., 2022; Nashikhah& Triyono, 2019). Thus, a graduate fashion designer who intends to achieve career success should be technical enough to understand the design process, elements of design and processes such as style and colour combination; sketching, embroidery, clothing accessories, and embellishment in fashion business venture (Eteng et al., 2022; Nashikhah & Triyono, 2019; Nzei, 2022). Business managerial skills include graduate fashion design practitioners' ability to network, negotiate, sell, market, manage time, finance, and staff adequately, and relate well with those who want to sew or design their materials. Personal skills enable the graduate fashion design entrepreneur to communicate effectively with customers, co-operate, and collaborate with others in the fashion industry (Nzei, 2022; Obiazi, 2021; Shillie & Nchang, 2023).

The above entrepreneurial skills could therefore determine how much success graduate fashion design practitioners attain in their fashion design career. For instance, a research showed that women's entrepreneurial skills significantly impacted their income in Borno State (Wuliya, 2022). Studies revealed significant impact of entrepreneurial competencies on performance of small-scale enterprises (SMEs) operating in Northwest and North-eastern, Nigeria (Danibrahim et al., 2022; Yunusa, 2023). However, studies are lacking on the influence of entrepreneurship skills and career success of graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo state. This study sought to find out if entrepreneurship skills are responsible for the level of career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo state.

Statement of the Problem

As a result of the huge scarcity of employment opportunities, many graduates in Oyo state delved into various kinds of entrepreneurial enterprises such as fashion design practice. However, many of them are yet to attain career success in the venture. Studies show low career success among many graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo state (Adegbenle, 2021; Adeleke & Ojewale, 2023; Ashamu & Olateju, 2023; Ayodele, 2021; Obialo & Adelore, 2023; Oghenovo, 2022; Osuntayo, 2017). Some of the graduate fashion design practitioners do not earn enough income to meet their needs and that of their family. Some of them are still not able to purchase lands, houses, cars, and various assets despite being in the fashion industry for quite some time. Some are still unable to expand their business, employ others and be satisfied despite being in the fashion design business for a long period of time ((Adegbenle, 2021;

Adeleke & Ojewale, 2023; Ashamu & Olateju, 2023; Ayodele, 2021; Obialo & Adelore, 2023; Oghenovo, 2022; Osuntayo, 2017). This study thus sought to investigate whether a crucial factor like entrepreneurship skills maybe influencing career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo state.

Research Questions

This study attempted to find answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State?
2. Do graduate fashion design practitioners have the needed entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, business management skills and personal skills) for fashion design practice in Oyo State?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There will be no significant joint contribution of entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, business management skills and personal skills) on career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State; and

H₀₂: There will be no significant relative influence of entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, business management skills and personal skills) on career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State.

Methodology

This research employed the descriptive survey research design. The target population comprised all male and female graduate fashion design practitioners (1,445) in three popular and highly busy local government areas (Lagelu, Kajola and Ibadan North) across the three senatorial districts in Oyo State. The Taro Yamane sample size determination formula was used to arrive at a sample size of eight hundred and thirty-six (836) graduate fashion design practitioners for the study. A researcher-constructed questionnaire titled: "Entrepreneurship Skills and Career Success Questionnaire (ESCSQ) was used to collect data. The questionnaire was validated using content and face validity and subjected to Cronbach's alpha for estimation of its internal consistency (stability). Value of .814 was obtained which meant that the questionnaire is stable (that is, reliable). The instrument was made into copies and administered

to the sample number (836) of graduate fashion design practitioners. However, 821 copies were retrieved. Demographic variables of graduate fashion design practitioners were analysed using frequency and percentage. Research questions were answered using frequency counts, percentages, mean, and standard deviation while inferential statistics such as multiple regression was used to analyse the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Data of Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n= 821)

Demographic Variables	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	321	39.1
Female	500	60.9
Age (Years)		
20 and below	100	12.2
21-30	298	36.3
31-40	302	36.8
41-50	105	12.8
51 and above	16	1.9
Highest Academic Qualification		
NCE	110	13.4
OND	201	24.5
HND	224	27.3
Bachelor's Degree	236	28.7
Master's Degree	50	6.1
Years of Fashion Design Practice		
1-5	258	31.4
6-10	306	37.3
11-15	201	24.5
16 and above	56	6.8

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 1 showed that 321 respondents in the study representing 39.1% are male graduate fashion design practitioners while 500 respondents representing 60.9% are females. Majority of the respondents, 302 (36.8%) are within 31-40 years of age, 236 (28.7%) have Bachelor's degree, and 306 (37.3%) have 6-10 years of experience. This result implies that majority among the graduate fashion design practitioners are university graduates and have above 5 years of experience in fashion design practice which is commendable.

Answer to Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the level of career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State?

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Table 2: Level of Acquisition of Assets among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	I have acquired more sewing machines including industrial, embroidery and stoning machines through my fashion practice	201 (24.5%)	358 (43.6%)	147 (17.9%)	115 (14.0%)	2.786	.713
2.	I have acquired more shops through fashion practice	120 (14.6%)	257 (31.3%)	200 (24.4%)	244 (29.7%)	2.308	.998
3.	I have landed properties through fashion design practice	110 (13.4%)	201 (24.5%)	308 (37.5%)	202 (24.6%)	2.267	1.010
4.	I have bought at least a car through fashion practice	205 (25.0%)	315 (38.4%)	198 (24.1%)	103 (12.5%)	2.758	.716

Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.530 (.859); Decision = Moderate Level

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Key: High Level (HL) = 4, Moderate Level (ML) = 3, Low Level (LL) = 2, Very Low Level (VLL) = 1; Std. Dev. = Standard Deviation; **Threshold Mean:** 1.000-1.750 = Very Low Level; 1.751-2.500 = Low Level; 2.501-3.250 = Moderate Level and 3.251 to 4.000 = High Level

Table 2 showed the level of career success in area of acquisition of assets among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The rating scale of Very Low Level (1) to High Level (4) was used. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.530$) clearly indicates that generally, the level of acquisition of assets among the graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level (slightly above low level).

Table 3 Level of Employment Generation among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std.Dev.
1.	My fashion design practice have provided new opportunities for paid employment	199 (24.2%)	210 (25.6%)	214 (26.1%)	198 (24.1%)	2.499	.983
2.	I have workers on my payroll in my fashion enterprise	153 (18.6%)	269 (32.8%)	201 (24.5%)	198 (24.1%)	2.459	.987
3.	I pay my workers very well in my fashion design enterprise	141 (17.2%)	249 (30.3%)	175 (21.3%)	256 (31.2%)	2.335	1.001

4.	I pay my workers regularly as at when due in my fashion design enterprise	138 (16.8%)	239 (29.1%)	209 (25.5%)	235 (28.6%)	2.341	.995
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Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.409 (.992); Decision = Low Level

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 3 showed the level of career success in area of employment generation among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.409$) clearly indicates that generally, the level of employment generation among the graduate fashion design practitioners is at a low level.

Table 4 Level of Family Needs Attainment among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	I am able to take proper care of my household meeting all their basic needs through fashion practice	296 (36.1%)	367 (44.7%)	112 (13.6%)	46 (5.6%)	3.112	.682
2.	I have been able to further my education and that of my family members single handedly through my fashion design practice	237 (28.9%)	251 (30.6%)	158 (19.2%)	175 (21.3%)	2.670	.874
3.	I am able to provide my family desires with ease at any given period of time without any form of financial stress	187 (22.8%)	249 (30.3%)	250 (30.5%)	135 (16.4%)	2.594	.916
4.	My family members have never lacked any essential needs as a result of my fashion design practice	193 (23.5%)	218 (26.6%)	262 (31.9%)	148 (18.0%)	2.555	.923

Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.733 (.849); Decision = Moderate Level

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 showed the level of career success in area of family needs attainment among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.733$) clearly indicates that generally, the level of family needs attainment among the graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level.

Table 5: Level of Career Satisfaction among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std.Dev.
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1.	I am fulfilled doing fashion design practice	200 (24.4%)	238 (29.0%)	240 (29.2%)	143 (17.4%)	2.603	.904
2.	I have passion for fashion design practice as it is what I have always wanted to do	202 (24.6%)	236 (28.7%)	218 (26.6%)	165 (20.1%)	2.579	.918
3.	My current expectations in fashion design practice is what I wanted to achieve	140 (17.1%)	202 (24.6%)	300 (36.5%)	179 (21.8%)	2.369	.990
4.	I am excited, joyful, happy and have a sense of self-actualization in my fashion design practice	198 (24.1%)	203 (24.7%)	296 (36.1%)	124 (15.1%)	2.579	.918

Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.533 (.933); Decision = Moderate Level

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 5 showed the level of career success in area of career satisfaction among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.533$) clearly indicates that generally, the level of career satisfaction among the graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level.

Research Question Two: Do graduate fashion design practitioners have the needed entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, business management skills and personal skills) for fashion design practice in Oyo State?

Table 6: Level of Technical Skills among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std.Dev.
1.	I have specialty in various aspects of fashion design such as drawing, cutting, pattern drafting, quilting, corsets, stitching, weaving, stoning and embroidery	218 (26.6%)	306 (37.3%)	204 (24.8%)	93 (11.3%)	2.790	.711
2.	I am able to effectively use all kinds of machines in fashion designing or tailoring such as stoning machines, embroidery machines, weaving or serger machines, quilting machines,	222 (27.0%)	284 (34.6%)	246 (30.0%)	69 (8.4%)	2.803	.706

	and sewing machines be it manual, industrial or computerized						
3.	I am able to solve fashion design or tailoring problems within a short time and still suit customer's taste	272 (33.1%)	301 (36.7%)	211 (25.7%)	37 (4.5%)	2.984	.695
4.	I effectively design and sew traditional and English wears, ready to wear outfit and clothes for mass market	224 (27.3%)	242 (29.5%)	248 (30.2%)	107 (13.0%)	2.710	.721
5.	I am able to effectively train others in all aspects of fashion design such as drawing, cutting, pattern drafting, corsets, stitching, weaving, quilting, stoning and embroidery	216 (26.3%)	254 (30.9%)	256 (31.2%)	95 (11.6%)	2.720	.722
Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.801 (.711); Decision = Moderate Level							

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 6 showed the level of technical entrepreneurial skill for fashion design practice among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.801$) clearly indicates that generally, the technical entrepreneurial skills for fashion design practice among graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level.

Table 7: Level of Business Management Skills among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	I communicate to my customers (new and existing) very well to the extent that none complain about my manner of approach	296 (36.1%)	305 (37.1%)	203 (24.7%)	17 (2.1%)	3.072	.612
2.	I market myself and my products regularly to the point that I get results from it	268 (32.6%)	271 (33.0%)	201 (24.5%)	81 (9.9%)	2.884	.699
3.	I have the ability to make people around me work together without conflicts	256 (31.2%)	281 (34.2%)	254 (30.9%)	30 (3.7%)	2.929	.687
4.	I am effective in planning my time to the point of delivering my services to clients before deadlines	198 (24.1%)	275 (33.5%)	266 (32.4%)	82 (10.0%)	2.717	.720

5.	I am able to properly account for all my income (earnings), expenditures/expenses, profits and losses leaving no stone unturned	202 (24.6%)	284 (34.6%)	292 (35.6%)	43 (5.2%)	2.786	.703
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Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.878 (.684); Decision = Moderate Level

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 7 showed the level of business management entrepreneurial skill for fashion design practice among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.878$) clearly indicates that generally, the business management entrepreneurial skills for fashion design practice among graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level.

Table 8: Level of Personal Skills among Graduate Fashion Design Practitioners (n = 821)

No.	Items	HL	ML	LL	VLL	Mean	Std.Dev.
1.	I am able to innovate or create new designs that are novel	215 (26.2%)	246 (30.0%)	212 (25.8%)	148 (18.0%)	2.643	.876
2.	I am able to save over 30% of what I earn and invest accordingly	158 (19.2%)	200 (24.4%)	368 (44.8%)	95 (11.6%)	2.513	.901
3.	I easily adapt to any new or latest trend in fashion and styling regardless of how complex they may be	199 (24.2%)	288 (35.1%)	230 (28.0%)	104 (12.7%)	2.709	.712
4.	I have self-confidence that I can take up new fashion jobs even though they are on areas I know little about and still deliver excellently	281 (34.2%)	264 (32.2%)	205 (25.0%)	71 (8.6%)	2.920	.680
5.	I spend a lot of time regardless of pressures/deadlines in making sure materials are well cut and sewn to exact customer's taste/preference	245 (29.8%)	328 (40.0%)	152 (18.5%)	96 (11.7%)	2.879	.704

Average Mean (Standard Deviation) = 2.733 (.775); Decision = Moderate Level

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 8 showed the level of personal entrepreneurial skill for fashion design practice among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviation, frequencies and percentages. The average mean ($\bar{x} = 2.733$) clearly

indicates that generally, the personal entrepreneurial skills for fashion design practice among graduate fashion design practitioners is at a moderate level.

Test of Hypotheses

H01: There will be no significant joint contribution of entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, business management skills and personal skills) on career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State

Table 9: Multiple Regression Analysis and Model Summary

		Anova					
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-Value	Decision
1	Regression	1510.121	4	377.530	15.227	.000	Significant
	Residual	20232.151	816	24.794			
	Total	21742.272	820				

Model Summary
R = .263
R Square = .069
Adjusted R Square = .065
Standard Error of the Estimate = 4.97936

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Dependent Variable: career success among graduate fashion design practitioners
Predictors: (Constant), personal skills, business management skills, technical skills
*F-value is significant at 0.05**

Table 9 shows a significant joint contribution of entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, business management skills and personal skills) on the career success among graduate fashion design practitioners ($F_{4, 816} = 15.227, P < 0.05$). Based on the model summary ($R = .263; R^2 = .069; \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .065; \text{standard error of the estimate} = 4.97936$), the adjusted r-square value (.065) showed that a 6.5% variability in career success of graduate fashion design practitioners can be explained by availability of acquisition of equipment and entrepreneurial skills. The remaining 93.5% of the variability in career success is caused by factors other than the predictors in the model.

H₀₂: There will be no significant relative influence of entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, business management skills and personal skills) on career success (acquisition of assets, employment generation, family needs attainment and career satisfaction) among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State.

Table 10: Coefficients of Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Coefficients			t	P-value
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Standard Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	25.418	1.186		21.432	.000
Technical Skills	.210	.043	.176	4.884	.001*
Business Management Skills	.208	.064	.165	3.250	.009*
Personal Skills	.198	.071	.144	2.789	.016*

Dependent Variable: career success among graduate fashion design practitioners

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

*Beta Coefficients significant at P<0.05

Table 10 clearly shows that technical skills ($\beta = .176$; $t = 4.884$; $P < 0.05$), business management skills ($\beta = .165$; $t = 3.250$; $P < 0.05$), and personal skills ($\beta = .144$; $t = 2.789$; $P < 0.05$) all exert relative influence on career success of graduate fashion design practitioners. The unstandardized coefficients (B) for the predictor variables showed that a unit increase in technical skills caused an increase (the positive sign of the coefficient) in career success of graduate fashion design practitioners by 0.210. A unit increase in business management skills caused an increase (the positive sign of the coefficient) in career success of graduate fashion design practitioners by 0.208. Lastly, a unit increase in personal skills caused an increase (the positive sign of the coefficient) in career success of graduate fashion design practitioners by 0.198.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined entrepreneurship skills and career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State, Nigeria. Research question one clearly indicates that the level of career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State in areas of acquisition of assets, family needs attainment and career satisfaction is at a moderate level but low level in area of employment generation. The above finding completely disagrees with a work on “entrepreneurial innovativeness and profitability of students’ start-ups” which revealed high

profitability (96%) of students' start-ups profitability or career success in Lagos and Ogun States (Ogbari et al., 2023). Furthermore, the results partially agrees with the work of Adeleke and Ojewale (2023) who established that the level at which youths in Oyo state are developing their career in various business ventures is at a moderate level.

Research question two clearly indicates that generally, graduate fashion design practitioners have moderate level of technical skills, business management skills and personal skills for fashion design practice. The above result is also similar to a work on "women's entrepreneurial skills acquisition and households' income in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State" which revealed moderate level of entrepreneurial skills acquisition among women fashion design practitioners (Wuliya, 2022). This result is also in line with that of a study on "fashion designing skills' acquisition and employability of social studies graduates in labour markets in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria" which revealed moderate level of fashion designing skill acquisition among social studies graduates in labour market (Unimna et al., 2021). Another study on "assessment of clothing and textiles occupational skills need and utilization for entrepreneurship among university undergraduates in South-South Zone, Nigeria" also renders support to the above result as it reveals a moderate level of occupational skills among clothing and textiles undergraduates (Obiazi et al., 2021).

The test of hypothesis one clearly indicates a significant joint contribution of entrepreneurship skills (technical skills, business management skills and personal skills) on the career success among graduate fashion design practitioners in Oyo State. The result agrees completely with the work which revealed that both human resource such as personal skills and material resources significantly impact on Entrepreneurship in Anambra Metropolis of Anambra State (Iwogbe et al., 2022). This finding is supported by a work on "fashion designing skills' acquisition and employability of social studies graduates in labour markets in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria" which revealed that fashion designing skill acquisition and resources do significantly influence employability of social studies graduates in labour market (Unimna et al., 2021).

The test of hypothesis two clearly indicates that technical skills, business management skills, and personal skills all exert positive relative influence on career success of graduate fashion design practitioners. The above finding agrees with a work on "entrepreneurial innovativeness

and profitability of students' start-ups" which revealed a significant relative influence of technical innovative skill on profitability or career success of students' start-ups in Lagos and Ogun States (Ogbari et al., 2023). Furthermore, the result of this study is also similar to a work on "women's entrepreneurial skills acquisition and households' income in Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State" which revealed relative influence of entrepreneurial skills (technical skills, business management skills and soft skills) acquisition on household income among women fashion design practitioners (Wuliya, 2022). This result is also in line with a work on "entrepreneurship in fashion design business ventures at retirement" which revealed that technical skills such as pattern making skill, clothing construction and design skills, business and soft skills and resources are significant on profitability of fashion design business (Nzei, 2022).

Conclusion

It can be concluded that moderate level of technical skills, business management skills and personal skills of the graduate fashion design practitioners are responsible for their moderate level of career success in areas of acquisition of assets, family needs attainment, and career satisfaction and low level of career success in area of employment generation in Oyo state, Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. The graduate fashion design practitioners should therefore do all they can either by working smarter or harder to ensure that they are able to increase boost their career success.
2. Majority of the graduate fashion design practitioners should undergo various seminars, trainings, and workshops to hone their skills so as to boost their productivity and increase their career success from slightly above low level to a high level.

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